

PREDICTION OF WATER QUALITY STATUS USING EXPLAINABLE MACHINE LEARNING MODELS

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Abstract— Water quality is critical for human health, aquatic ecosystems, and sustainable development, especially in climate-vulnerable coastal regions of Bangladesh. Secondary data were collected from the publicly available Hydroshare database. This study used four machine learning algorithms: Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Decision Tree (DT), and Random Forest (RF) to predict water quality using physicochemical and microbiological parameters. Water quality was classified into two categories based on the Water Quality Index (WQI). SVM and RF achieved the highest accuracy (97%), followed by DT (92%), while LR showed lower performance (65%). SHAP analysis identified pH, dissolved oxygen, nitrate, and temperature as the most influential factors, followed by fecal coliform, BOD, and total coliform. The results demonstrate that machine learning, combined with explainable AI, can provide accurate and interpretable water-quality predictions for environmental monitoring and decision-making.

Keywords— Water Quality Prediction, Machine Learning, SHAP, Environmental Monitoring.

I. INTRODUCTION

Water is one of the most crucial resources for life on Earth. Water covers over three-quarters of the Earth's surface, making it an essential natural resource for all living things [1]. Many organisms can survive for a short time without other resources, but none can survive without water. Rapid population growth, industrialization, and urbanization have intensified water pollution. Existing studies often struggle to identify key water quality factors and model complex environmental relationships. Machine learning and SHAP can improve prediction accuracy and interpretability.

II. METHODOLOGY

The framework integrates multiple machine learning models, hyperparameter optimization, and SHAP-based explainable AI to improve prediction accuracy and identify the most influential water quality parameters.

A. Propose Machine Learning Models

The classification framework consists of Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Decision Tree (DT), and Random Forest (RF) models. These algorithms utilize probabilistic, margin-based, tree-based, and ensemble-learning approaches, respectively, to classify water quality and improve predictive performance.

B. Explainability Analysis

SHAP is an explainable AI technique based on Shapley values that quantifies feature contributions to model predictions, providing both global and local interpretability [2].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental results demonstrated the superior performance of RF and SVM, both achieving 97% accuracy. DT achieved 92% accuracy, whereas LR showed the lowest performance (65%). Table 1 summarizes the classification results of all models.

Table 1. Model's performance comparison

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Accuracy
LR	0.76	0.65	0.68	0.65
DT	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.92
RF	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97
SVM	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97

Figure 1. SHAP Summary Plot.

Figure 1 shows the SHAP summary plot for the RF. pH was the most important predictor, followed by DO, nitrate, and temperature, while microbiological parameters had comparatively lower influence on model predictions.

IV. CONCLUSION

RF and SVM achieved the best performance, while SHAP identified the key predictive factors. Future work will explore real-time applications.

References

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